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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

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Final Report on the creation and awarding of the R&I Prize in the final year of the ENLIGHT RISE programme, the lessons learnt.

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List of abbreviations

D	Deliverable (within the ENLIGHT RISE project)
DG RTD	The European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
EUA	European University Alliance
ECR	Early Career Researcher
GA	Grant Agreement (H2020 SwafS GA number 101035819)
M	Month, i.e. project month being September 2021 M1, and August 2024 M36
PO	Project Officer
PU	Partner university
R&I	Research and Innovation
SwafS	the Horizon 2020 <i>Science with and for Society</i> work programme
WP	Work Package
Y	project year (from September 1 st to August 1 st ; Y1 = 2021-2022)

Introduction

[ENLIGHT](#) is a European University Alliance (EUA) willing to promote equitable quality of life, sustainability, and global engagement through higher education transformation. ENLIGHT brings together [nine comprehensive research-intensive universities](#) from nine European countries.

ENLIGHT has obtained funding from the European Commission in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Science with and for Society (SwafS) work programme. The thus created [ENLIGHT RISE project](#) (Research and Innovation agenda with and for SociEty) seeks to strengthen the research and innovation (R&I) dimension of the ENLIGHT alliance. In synergy with ENLIGHT's educational components and surrounding ecosystems, ENLIGHT RISE strives to deploy a comprehensive joint transformation agenda for our universities.

The R&I Prize is a product of the ENLIGHT RISE Work Package 2 (WP2) which main objective is to create synergies through R&I capacity building and to contribute to establish a common Research & Innovation agenda.

Comprised of three major tasks (groups), WP2 seeks to complement the mapping of expertise in the ENLIGHT Think Tank (cfr. the ENLIGHT Erasmus+ project) by analysing the alliance members' scientific and technological profiles to identify the strongest research synergies leading to maximize the ENLIGHT alliance's competitive advantage (task 2.1).

The *R&I Observatory* (task 2.2) will help identifying the ENLIGHT R&I capacities, whilst focus groups and incentives mechanisms (task 2.3) will enable to establish R&I synergies amongst the alliance's partner universities.

The R&I Prize is one of the incentive mechanisms developed within the cradle of WP2 task 2.3, intended to be awarded yearly (i.e. every project year) throughout the lifespan of the ENLIGHT RISE project (01 September 2021 – 31 August 2024).

This active document is the third and final report on the R&I Prize throughout the lifespan of the ENLIGHT RISE SwafS funding period. It represents Deliverable (D)15 (D2.7) on the construction, awarding, and evaluation the R&I Prize. This document is hence an update of D13 (D2.5) and D14 (D2.6) and therefore adopts the text of the foregoing deliverables, complementing them with progress on the R&I Prize made in Y3 and the final evaluation. The text in blue italics highlights the specific additions for D15 (from page 18 and onwards).

R&I Prize Year 1

Context and intention

Being a new university alliance consisting of university partners who in various research fields have not yet enjoyed previous interactions, the EUA ENLIGHT RISE consortium seeks to create incentives for the launching of several initiatives fostering research & innovation collaborations amongst its partner universities, specifically around the ENLIGHT [flagship domains](#) (health & well-being; digital revolution and impact of digitization; climate change; energy and circular economy; equity).

In addition to that, the consortium i.a. also focuses on early career researchers (ECR) – defined as researchers holding a PhD. less than 10 years –, recognizing their driving force for new initiatives, their imminent need for funding, as well as their necessity to create personal international research networks.

With the intention of combining the abovementioned goals, the ENLIGHT RISE project proposal conceived “the creation of an annual contest / competition to award Prizes for the best ENLIGHT RISE R&I projects on ENLIGHT flagship challenges conducted by early career researchers from 2 or more ENLIGHT partner universities (...)”. The prizes, thus to be considered as seed funding, were to “primarily consist of travel awards to attend a specialized conference, workshop, or training programme that will contribute to capacity building in ENLIGHT”.

The creation of the Prize(s) was added to WP2 as Task 2.3.2 “Create incentives for launching joint R&I projects around flagship challenges (M6-36)”.

Concept

During its meeting of February 18th, 2022, the ENLIGHT RISE WP2 assembly discussed Task 2.3.2 and after deliberating different options and concepts decided to create the annual *ENLIGHT CONSORTIUM R&I PRIZE* as a two-step system allocating not only travel awards but also a proper ENLIGHT R&I Prize. In this two-fold design, only awardees of a travel award are eligible for the ENLIGHT R&I Prize. The intention thereof, is to first incentivize ECRs towards collaborative ENLIGHT R&I projects, and then in a second phase reward amongst those projects the most promising one.

With regards to the selection committee for both the travel awards as the R&I prize, WP2 decided to populate the committee with 9 members: one (1) task member of each ENLIGHT RISE WP2 (co)-lead partner university (i.e. University of Bordeaux, Ghent University, University of the Basque Country, University of Tartu), added to the coordinators of each of the five (5) pilot focus groups (WP2 Task 2.3.1). Considering the likelihood that for the first selection period/year the pilot focus groups would not (all) have been created yet – and to bridge with the ENLIGHT E+ project – it was decided that for the first year of the prize the 5 heads of the pilot focus groups would be replaced by the heads of the five ENLIGHT E+ Think Thanks/Core Groups.

The call for the first ENLIGHT R&I Prize was published/launched in July 2022 (with deadline October 1st, 2022) with a retro-active character for the R&I Prize to cover the entire first project year of ENLIGHT RISE project. The call was widely disseminated and promoted both by the alliance as by the ENLIGHT partners universities through different channels as i.a. the ENLIGHT website and [ENLIGHT funding](#)

[webpage](#), the ENLIGHT newsletters, the ENLIGHT Twitter account, partner universities' funding pages and social media, as well as via specifically target group directed mailings by all partner institutes.

Further details on this system, eligibility, selection criteria, submission and reporting are explained at length in the actual call and application form, both below inserted within this report.

The call for the ENLIGHT CONSORTIUM R&I PRIZE Y1

ENLIGHT CONSORTIUM R&I PRIZE

Call for R&I projects and initiatives around the ENLIGHT flagship areas between early career researchers from different ENLIGHT consortium partners.
(ENLIGHT R&I PRIZE)

In the framework of this call, the [ENLIGHT consortium](#) will grant travel/mobility awards and the ENLIGHT R&I Prize Award for the best R&I (envisioned) projects and project proposals jointly conducted by early career researchers from different (minimum 2) ENLIGHT consortium partners.

In a first phase, selected project proposals will receive an ENLIGHT R&I Prize Travel Award to help deepen the envisioned plans (new or ongoing) for collaboration. The aim of this seed money is to stimulate and support (new) ENLIGHT RISE R&I collaborations and projects on ENLIGHT flagship challenges between early career researchers from various/different consortium partners.

In a second phase, the awarded projects making promising progress towards a consolidated joint R&I collaboration after having received the travel award will automatically be selected as candidates for the annual ENLIGHT R&I Prize.

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The annual ENLIGHT R&I Prize

Concept:

The ENLIGHT R&I Prize is an annual competition awarding promising joint collaborations – in research fields linked to the [5 ENLIGHT flagship domains](#) – between early career researchers from different ENLIGHT consortium partners. The aim is not only to enhance overall R&I collaborations between ENLIGHT consortium partners, moreover, to support early career researchers in expanding their network.

The design of the prize is two-fold. While the first part consists of seed funding through an open call for travel awards to (further) elaborate collaboration ideas, the second part is the actual ENLIGHT R&I Prize, annually presented during the ENLIGHT General Meeting rewarding the most promising result of the initiatives having received a travel award in the first phase of the ENLIGHT R&I Prize.

Applying project proposals must contribute to the research mission of ENLIGHT, and hence focus on the development of (new) joint research initiatives amongst ENLIGHT partners. These research initiatives must focus on the 5 ENLIGHT flagship domains and correspond to major societal challenges and priorities (health and well-being, climate action, energy transition and circular economy, digital innovation (AI / Open Science), and equity).

Phase 1: The ENLIGHT R&I Prize Travel Award

The ENLIGHT R&I Prize is intended as seed money to support the development stage or further elaboration of joint research activities conducted by early career researchers of different (minimum 2) ENLIGHT consortium partners, e.g. the initiation, design and/or development of one (or more) joint research proposals to be submitted to regional, national or international funding agencies including the Horizon Europe framework programme, etc.

The first phase of the ENLIGHT R&I Prize therefore aims to facilitate in-person meetings and mobility between these early career researchers to concretize their collaboration, and/or to help them acquire necessary skills required to further elaborate their idea/project.

Applying projects therefore can apply for the following two activities:

1. outgoing mobility of staff and PhD students to participate in meetings at one of the other ENLIGHT partners with the purpose of setting up new or enlarging already existing bilateral or multilateral research collaborations. Only the mobility costs (travel and subsistence) of the applicant are eligible.
2. attendance to a specialized conference, workshop, or training programme to enhance capacity needed for the envisioned joint project. Only the mobility costs (travel and subsistence) and inscription fees of the applicant are eligible.

Each yearly edition, about 10 travel awards are foreseen to be awarded of maximum EUR 500.- each. Only the mobility costs (travel and subsistence) and/or the inscription fee of the applicant are eligible, and the funding will be through reimbursement of proven expenditures. Reimbursement will be done by the University of Bordeaux's administration to the applicant's home institute for further internal allocation.

Applying projects can apply for maximum three individual travel awards per project. In case of selection, it will be up to the selection committee to decide how many travel awards it will allocate to each selected project.

In case of outgoing mobility to attend meetings at an ENLIGHT consortium partner, a financial commitment (co-funding) of the receiving ENLIGHT partner is advised (share in organizational costs or mobility). Recommended for joint research related ENLIGHT activities, is that the 'sending'

university accounts for the funding of travel and accommodation of the own outgoing staff and PhD students/researchers while the host university accounts for any organizational costs of the activity applied for. In this respect, the seed funding R&I Prize Travel Award can be used by the sending university to support the researchers' mobility.

Phase 2: The ENLIGHT R&I Prize Award

Awardees of the first phase will automatically apply for the second phase once the report (cfr. below) of the first phase has been accepted by the ENLIGHT R&I Prize Secretariat. Projects can thus not directly solicit nor apply for prize but will be considered for the ENLIGHT R&I Prize Award upon their selection for the ENLIGHT R&I Prize Travel Award and the acceptance of their report (of which they will be duly notified by the prize secretariat).

The selection will be done annually beginning of November, and the award winner will be contacted prior to the award ceremony.

The winner of the ENLIGHT R&I Prize will be announced annually during the ENLIGHT General Meeting. The prize consists of maximum EUR 1,500.- to be used for (or reimbursement of) registration, attendance, mobility costs, etc. of a conference, workshop, or training programme to enhance capacity needed for the project. The funding will be through reimbursement of proven expenditures and will be done by the University of Bordeaux's administration to the applicant's home institute for further internal allocation.

Criteria

Who can apply:

Staff members (including doctoral researchers/students) of ENLIGHT consortium partners:

- the main applicant(s), beneficiary(/ies), or project leader(s) must be (an) early career researcher(s) (i.e. doctoral student or a researcher who has obtained the PhD title no longer than 9 years prior to the R&I Prize application date)
- an eligible project (or the reimbursed activity) must include members of minimum two different ENLIGHT consortium partners.

Disciplinary field:

Proposals should focus on one of the 5 the ENLIGHT [flagship domains](https://www.enlight-eu.org/university-about-us/flagship-domains) (health and well-being, climate action, energy transition and circular economy, digital innovation (AI / Open Science), and equity) as described on the above linked webpage (<https://www.enlight-eu.org/university-about-us/flagship-domains>).

Activities eligible for funding:

The present call targets the organization, creation, and exploration of (new) joint R&I activities and opportunities between ENLIGHT partners and will provide travel awards for the project members to meet in-person or to attend a specialised training, conference or workshop related to the project:

- the mobility / travel award therefore must be used to physically meet amongst the project members to prepare the project, or to jointly attend a specialized conference, workshop, or training programme to enhance capacity needed for the project.
- the activity (mobility) must be / have been conducted between September 1st 2021 and October 1st 2022.

Deadline

The call for the first annual ENLIGHT R&I Prize is open on a permanent basis until October 1st, 2022.

Selection

The selection of applying project proposals will be based on following criteria:

- Accordance with the [overall ENLIGHT objective/mission](#)
- Role of the applicant in the project
- Feasibility
- Innovative character
- Sustainability
- Involvement of the [Regional Academies](#) (i.e. focus on quadruple helix)

The selection commission will be composed of experts on the [ENLIGHT flagship domains](#) and one (1) task member of each ENLIGHT RISE WP2 (co)-lead partner university. Prior to the proclamation of the awardees, the ENLIGHT RISE WP2 assembly will validate the pre-selected winners.

How to apply?

Applications are made through the [designated form](#) and sent as a PDF-document to rise@ugent.be.

The document should be named as follows:

ENLIGHT_R-I_Prize_-_surname_MainApplicant_name_MainApplicant

Reporting of awarded prizes

Within one month after the end of the funded activity (and/or no later the October 20th, 2022), a short report (max. 1 A4), signed by the main applicant, together with the proven expenditure, must be sent electronically to rise@ugent.be.

Upon acceptance of the report, the project will be notified of its pre-selection for the ENLIGHT R&I Prize Award, and the applicant's home partner institute will be reimbursed the ENLIGHT R&I Prize Travel Award.

To be eligible for the ENLIGHT R&I Prize Award, the report should illustrate the progress of the idea/concept/project since the awarding of the ENLIGHT R&I Prize Travel Award. (i.e. the reimbursed activity).

ENLIGHT CONSORTIUM R&I PRIZE

Call for ENLIGHT ECR R&I initiatives

Application Form 2021-2022

1. Proposal title + Acronym

2. Please indicate the flagship domain your project relates to

- Health and Well-being
- Digital revolution and Impact of digitization
- Climate change
- Energy and Circular economy
- Equity

3. Main focus of the proposal (Please also state the involved ENLIGHT Consortium partners¹)

4. Personal details of the (Main) applicant

Full Name	
Position	
Faculty/Research Unit/Department	
ENLIGHT University	
Email	

5. Personal details of any other ENLIGHT applicants (only in case of a multiple application; max. 3 travel awards can be awarded per proposal)

Full Name	
Position	
Faculty/Research Unit/Department	
ENLIGHT University	
Email	

Please copy the above table as many times as needed

6. Personal details of ENLIGHT partners (i.e. researchers) involved (not applying for a travel award)

Full Name	
-----------	--

Position	
Faculty/Research Unit/Department	
ENLIGHT University	
Email	

Please copy the above table as many times as needed

7. General description of the initiative/project and the role of the applicant in the project (max. 600 words)

8. Main objectives and output (max. 250 words)

9. Timing of planned activities of the preparatory phase and implementation (max. 250 words)

10. Parallel applications

Did you or will you apply for funding for these activities at any other organisation/grant or call?

No

Yes

⇒ Please further explain to which organisation, grant or call, and for what amount and which specific activities (max. 200 words):

11. Budget

Cost type	Description	Amount
Travel	<i>unit costs, #persons</i>	€ ...
Subsistence	<i>unit costs, #persons</i>	€ ...
Organization	<i>Venue, catering, other</i>	€ ...
	TOTAL	€ ...

12. Annexes (programme, invitation mail/letter, call text, ... please number and specify)

Annexe 1:

Annexe 2:

...

**KINDLY SEND IN YOUR APPLICATION FILE TO
RISE@UGENT.BE NO LATER THEN OCTOBER 1st, 2022**

Applications result

By the end of the application deadline, two (2) applications were received. Unfortunately, both applications resulted ineligible.

Not only did both application budgets exceed the set limited amount of the ENLIGHT R&I Prize Travel Award, moreover none of the entered applications explained how the described mobility – for which funding was requested – would serve the final purpose of one of the fundable activities as stated in the call. On top of that, the envisioned mobility of one of the applications fell outside of the fundable/specified time span as stipulated in the call.

Since no eligible application was received, the WP2 assembly decided (in its meeting of October 10th, 2022) not to allocate any travel awards nor an ENLIGHT R&I Prize in year 1, and to transfer the reserved funding for Y1 to Y2.

Lessons learned

The disappointing result of Y1 was evaluated both by the WP2 co-leads in a specific meeting on the topic on October 4th, 2022, as by the WP2 assembly in its beforementioned meeting of October 10th, 2022, with the intention to adapt the call for Y2 accordingly.

Five major reasons for the low response were identified:

1. *Limited funding amount*

Throughout the application period many researchers proclaimed that although the application process was very simple and not time-consuming, the amount of the travel award (i.e. € 500,-) was just not worth the effort and not sufficiently attractive. WP2 Members identified this as the major shortcoming of the Y1 concept since feedback had already showed that various funding officers and/or research support officers/offices did not promote the R&I Prize since the travel award in no case would cover the actual mobility cost, for which applicants would always direct their attention and efforts towards more appealing and comprehensive calls for mobility awards.

WP 2 hence evaluated that if the R&I prize was to be attractive and appealing, it would be imperative to raise the amount per mobility award, consequently also leading to a lower number of travel awards.

2. *Retro-active character and funding*

Applying for the reimbursement of a past mobility or activity resulted complicated and unusual. Once paid for, the urge to seek for and put effort into a redemption of a past mobility or inscription fee is not on the priority list of researchers and comes across as too administrative and time-consuming.

The unanimous feeling therefore is that future calls should be oriented towards future events, i.e. applicants should be entered for the funding of an event/mobility to come.

3. *'Prize award' deflects from mobility character*

Perhaps the concept of the dual /two-fold design and awarding process of the call was complicated and/or confusing for many researchers and therefore – also considering the minor price/mobility fee – withheld and discouraged researchers from applying. The assessment was made that future calls should emphasize the mobility aspect of the call and speak of mobility awards, rather than focusing on the awarding of a prize.

4. *Closed timeframe for eligible activities*

Since researchers probably mainly look for funding during the period, they organize their mobility and effectuate the inscription to events/conferences, the timespan during which the call was open (4 months during the summer period) limited the number of researchers that could be attracted to the call.

The WP members esteem that the effectiveness, relevance, and attractiveness of the travel awards/the R&I Prize would be far greater with an open call not indicating specific limited dates for refundable mobilities.

5. *Publication period*

Launching the call in July when most researchers start or prepare their summer recess was evaluated as not the ideal period. Although the call was widely published and promoted several times during and after summer recess, it did not stand out nor resonate amongst researchers.

WP 2 considered that the call would be more effective through a continuous call system enabling researchers to apply at any period of the year when the need for mobility support emerges.

Outlook Y2 & Y3: Renewed concept R&I PRIZE

Based on the abovementioned evaluation, the WP2 meeting has decided to accordingly adapt the concept of the ENLIGHT RISE R&I Prize.

In its meeting of October 10th, 2022, the decision was adopted that the outline of the new concept should thus be that of a continuously open call for future mobilities and/or participation to an event, to be hosted after receipt of the application and before the ending of the funding of the ENLIGHT RISE SwafS project (August 31st, 2024).

With the call being open, evaluation/selection of the received applications will be continuous and awarded on a first come, first serve basis. A fixed amount of mobility awards will be awarded for Y2 and Y3. Consequently, once the number of awards for a specific year has been allocated, the call for that specific year will be closed and the call for the next year will be opened.

The renewed R&I Prize will however uphold its two-fold character. At the end of each project year, the selection committee will evaluate the final reports of the mobility awards allocated in the respective year and select a winner of the ENLIGHT R&I Prize.

Finally, the WP2 assembly decided to increase the amount of the mobility award and the R&I Prize, by doubling it to € 1,000.- for the travel award, and raising it to a still unspecified amount higher than the original € 1,500.- for the ENLIGHT R&I Prize (workshop award). The ENLIGHT RISE Coordinator has thereto contacted the DG RTD PO informing her of this decision, since this implies a reduction in the number of awards.

During its meeting of November 18th, 2022, (post factum the editing of this report) the WP2 assembly will further discuss the outline and needed changes of the proposal for a renewed R&I Prize, with the intention to take the final decision during its meeting on December 16th, 2022, to be able to launch the Y2 R&I Prize no later than by the end of January 2023.

The outcome, concept, and evaluation of the R&I Prize Y2 will be attended to in D14/2.6, to be submitted by December 2023.

R&I Prize Year 2

Applied changes

As announced in D13, the decision was adopted to slightly alter the outline of the R&I Prize to enhance the attractiveness of the mobility award and make it overall more appealing for the consortium's researchers to apply.

First, in its meeting of November 18th, 2022, the WP2 assembly decided to confirm the earlier projected decision to raise the amount of both the mobility award and the R&I Prize. The available funding was thus distributed as follows:

	Y 2	Y3
Mobility award	10 x € 1.000,-	10 x € 1.000,-
Workshop award (i.e. ENLIGHT R&I Prize)	1 x € 5.000,-	1 x € 5.000,-

Second, whilst re-editing the R&I Prize (due the changed award amounts) and striving to tackle the complicated timeline forcing all project expenses to be settled by July-August 2024, a renewed proposal emerged for the R&I Prize and the mobility awards.

The new concept in separated – to a certain extent – both the prize and the mobility awards, with the intention to tackle the prize award form deflecting the mobility character of the travel awards (cf. supra, point 3 page 12). The idea was to promote both components of the R&I Prize separately from each other: whereas the mobility awards would be actively promoted, the R&I Prize Award would only be published on the ENLIGHT website enabling the mobility award to refer/link to it, but the prize award would not be promoted as such (and thus also no longer be extensively explained in the travel award call). The intention thus being to focus entirely on the travel awards, keeping the prize as a “on top off” for the most promising results coming out of the travel awards.

Furthermore, calls would no longer be launched per project year. Instead, an open call would be launched for the remainder of the project lifespan, rewarding mobility awards on a “first come first served principle”.

Summarizing, following were the key elements of the new call proposal:

- Regarding the mobility awards:
 - 20 ECR mobility awards (financing of actual costs) of max. € 1,000 each
 - The call is opened to receive proposals 1/1/2023 – 15/12/2023
=> keeping the call open longer, would make it difficult to select (a) prize winner(s) amongst mobility awardees who can still use the prize money before August 2024
 - Once 20 mobility awards have been allocated, the call is to be closed and removed from the ENLIGHT website
 - Intended for ECR => 10 years after obtaining PhD, doctoral students included
 - Mobility awards must be used prior to 1/4/2024

- => i.e. final reports of last used mobility award should be received by 1/5/2024
- Monthly selection/awarding of received applications
 - Selection committee: WP2 assembly upon suggestion made by WP2 co-leads
 - No change to the application form
- Regarding the R&I prize:
1. Launch an open call for ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Awards
 2. Select 2 R&I Prize award winners
 - every prize (financing of actual costs) = max. € 5,000- each, to be used for workshop, conference, training
 - prize amount should be used before 31/8/2024
 - selection based on the received (by the date of selection) mobility grants (progress) reports of the WP2 ECR Mobility Award
 - Date of selection: prize 1 -> September 2023; Prize 2 -> May 2024
→ selecting later would make it difficult to use the prize money prior 31/08/2024
 - selection committee = 1 pax per co-leads + 1 representative per focus group. Selection to be approved by the WP2 assemble.

After deliberation, the WP2 assembly accepted this new proposal in its meeting of December 9th, 2022. New call documents were thus edited for both the mobility awards and the R&I Prize. After their approval through e-mail consultation, the renewed Mobility Award and R&I Prize were relanced and published on the ENLIGHT website on December 22nd, 2022. (Cf. Annexes 1 and 2 for the renewed calls and the following links: [Mobility Award](#) ; [R&I Prize](#)).

All ENLIGHT partner universities widely dispersed the information on the mobility award and promoted it within their research community via newsletters, social media, specifically directed e-mails, etc. Alongside, the award was raised to the attention of all the members of the pilot focus groups.

Despite the implemented changes and the (combined) promotional efforts of all PUs, no applications were received during the last semester of Y2. After intense deliberation and consultations, we evaluate that the specific orientation of the R&I Prize towards ECRs mainly resulted more repulsive than attractive. Contrary to our initial believe, we learnt that ECRs are less interested then expected in the award, mainly due to two factors:

- 1) most ECR (especially doctoral students) don't have an expanded network, making it hard for them to apply for funding with other ENLIGHT partners researchers (whom they don't yet know), and
- 2) ECR mainly have different tasks and priorities than this type of funding; to be more precise, ECR mostly focus on paper-writing to boost their own academic path/career, and on project management of projects often coordinated by senior researchers.

Alongside, ECRs made it clear that many of them fitting within our definition of an ECR (i.e. having obtained a PhD no longer than 10 years ago) did not consider themselves an ECR and therefore did not read further on this funding opportunity since they believe the call would not apply to them; i.e. that they were not the focus of the call and thus would not be eligible.

Struggling in finding ECR applicants for the travel awards and capturing a necessity for mobility funding in the focus groups, we therefore sought permission from the PO (online meeting October 11th, 2023) to open the R&I prize and travel award to senior researchers. That way, the pilot focus group members

would be able to take usage of this resource to physically meet and prepare their collaboration and project proposal.

After the approval of the PO, we slightly adapted the call for the travel awards by taking out the requirement for applicants to be ECRs, now indicating that the call is open to: “All researchers registered or employed at ENLIGHT partners. Predoctoral researchers, PhD students as well as postdoctoral researchers and fellows are encouraged to apply” (cf. [the call criteria](#)).

This change resulted in immediate enhanced interest in the call, leading to multiple eligible applications (cf. [infra](#)).

Financial regulations

Reimbursing the awardees or transferring the amounts of the travel grants to the awardees proved more easily said than done.

With the provision of the R&I Prize allocated within the project budget of the coordinator (UBx), transferring provisions to researchers which are not on the payroll of UBx proved no evident task. Wiring the awardees allocated amount to the sending universities for them then to transfer it to the awardee furthermore proved disadvantageous since i.a. institutional overhead would lessen the actual amount disbursed to the researchers.

To tackle these issues, we agreed that UBx would handle the transfers directly with the awardee who therefore should comply with the financial and travel regulations of the UBx Financial Department. To that end, financial guidelines were established for the travel awards which are shared with the awardees along with their award letter¹.

Awarded Mobility Grants

Renewed promotional efforts of the mobility awards and opening it up to senior researchers in M25, led to an increase of interest in the mobility awards and consequential applications.

Between M24 and M27 (September - December 2023) 14 mobility awards have been allocated. Annex 3 provides a clear overview of the anonymized awardees information, their mobility finalities and research topics.

Most mobilities will take place end of 2023, beginning of 2024.

With one month left before the open call will be closed, we are confident that the remaining 6 travel awards will be allocated.

Unfortunately, these mobility grants (and more specifically the envisioned dates of their mobility) came too late to select an R&I Prize in Y2. However, the provisions of Y2 will be transferred to Y3 enabling us to select two R&I Prize winners in the final months of the project.

¹ Being internal UBx regulations, these are not shared in this public here, nevertheless, they remain at the disposal (can be requested by) of the European Commission.

R&I Prize Year 3

ENLIGHT RISE R&I Mobility Award

As mentioned above, the – in year 2 – newly adopted strategy immediately resulted in a steady influx of applications for the mobility awards. By the deadline (December 15th, 2023), in total fourteen valid applications had been received for twenty-one mobilities (four were group applications combining multiple individual mobility award).

The projected expenditure for these twenty-one mobility awards (i.e. the requested budget in the application + an estimation of the required sum for per diems and additional subsistence cost) mounted to € 17,531,-. Although this remained below the budgeted €20K for the mobility awards, the decision was taken, however, not to select additional applications (e.g. those who applied after the deadline) as extra unforeseen per diem or travel costs potential might still lift the final expenditure to the foreseen 21K.

By April 2024, however, it became clear that the opposite had occurred, and that awardees had spent vastly less than budgeted in their applications: only € 9,557.12 was spent out of the +17K EUR applied for.

Besides two awardees having to cancel their mobility (one quit her ENLIGHT partner university, another one cancelled due to health reasons), we believe the main reason for this to be the overbudgeting of subsistence costs at the applications phase.

In its meeting of April 19th, 2024, the WP2 assembly decided to select additional mobility awards using the same modalities as during the last call period (i.e. first-come-first-served principle, same application form, selection by mail through tacit consent directly to all WP2 members).

Time being short both for the application process and the implementation period (due to the ENLIGHT RISE project ending 31/8/2024 and the summer recess approaching rapidly), the decision was adopted to target 3 specific categories addressing them directly by mail: i) applicants/applications received shortly after the deadline of December 15, 2023, ii) members of the pilot focus groups and their sub-groups, offering them mobility awards to meet up and work on project proposals, iii) participants of the WP1 organized online matchmaking event (April 29, 2024) in light of the preparing of a proposal for the ENLIGHT 2.0 ETN call for thematic networks.

This has led to four additional awarded applications for in total eight mobility awards, lifting the total applied for budget to € 19,323,-.

The table in Annex 4 provides an overview of the anonymized final list of ENLIGHT RISE R&I Mobility Award winners.

The final expenditure on the mobility awards mounts to €15,223-, thus still falling short of the projected 21K. As abovementioned, we believe this is mainly due to some cancellations and to overestimation of the costs by applicants at application phase.

The table also shows that the initial intention of focusing the mobility awards on early stage researchers has – against all odds – largely been achieved with 23 out of 29 (i.e. 80%) awardees being early career researchers.

The reports send in by the awardees showed that initial contacts and long-lasting connections were made, but that in most cases these connections remained at initial phase (i.e. “good to know what the others are doing...”) and that immediate quick-wins mostly did not emerge.

ENLIGHT RISE R&I Prize

As previously mentioned, no R&I Prize was awarded in Year 2. Instead, two prizes of €5,000 each were available in Year 3.

Eligible recipients for these prizes were all mobility awardees who had submitted their reports by May 1, 2024. Unfortunately, the additional selected mobility awardees mentioned earlier did not qualify, as their mobilities occurred after May 2024.

The R&I Prize Selection Committee reviewed all mobility reports and identified the HACIDA and NEURO-BALANCE projects as the most promising outcomes of the mobility awards.

Both projects resulted in joint research applications for Horizon Europe projects and demonstrated that the collaborative links established during the mobilities would persist regardless of whether the submitted Horizon Europe proposals were funded. The R&I Prize could furthermore support these collaborations, allowing for continued progress in joint research and the solidification of research ideas at the core of both projects.

However, the timing of the R&I Prize was unfortunate since the expenditure period for ENLIGHT RISE SwafS funding was limited to August 31st, 2024 (the final day of the project lifespan). As a result, prize winners had only from May to August 2024 to utilize the €5,000 prize for mobilities or attendance at related conferences, workshops, or training events.

Given the coinciding examination schedules and summer recess in most universities, actually utilizing the R&I Prize during this period proved challenging. HACIDA only managed to use prize money to send one researcher from the university of Tartu to attend a conference in Riga from June 17th to 21th. NEURO-BALANCE to the contrary, did manage to use some of the awarded funds for a mobility effort and attendance to a specialized training, enriching their envisioned future collaboration and project proposals.

Conclusion

Overall, we may conclude that the awarding of the mobility awards and the R&I Prize was a difficult process and less successful as foreseen and hoped for during the proposal writing phase of the ENLIGHT RISE project.

The believe was that seed funding through mobility awards and an annual contest / competition to award R&I prizes would incentivize joint collaborations amongst the ENLIGHT RISE research community. In practise, it has proven hard to reach researchers and enthusiasm them into applying for mobility to visits colleagues at other (partner) universities they had no previous link with.

Though some new collaborations were started and successful – e.g. the HACIDA Horizon Europe proposal was awarded, resulting in the DELIAH project – the experience within Work Package 2 has thought us that researchers are more interested in first getting to know their fellow colleagues of a different research community through efforts like online matchmaking events (cf. WP1, deliverable D1.8) and focus groups (see WP2 tasks 2.3.1 and deliverable D16) rather than spending time and effort on visiting them as a first contact.

Probably the administrative nuisance of having to apply for, and organize a, mobility and the overall “loss” of time contributes to the lesser attractive way of engaging into new first contacts. Simultaneously, and with the ENLIGHT RISE project starting in the aftermath of COVID/19, we noticed that quick and time less intensive online meetings are more attractive to researchers compared to time invasive travel.

Administratively, the organisation of prizes and mobility awards throughout the consortium, with the funds residing at one partner, resulted complicated and a barrier for a smooth and swift organisation. Different administrative-financial stipulations (V.A.T.-regulations, overhead costs, etc) and travel policies between the partner universities make it hard to synchronize the effort, and complicate the transfer of funds to individual researchers from a different institution.

We can therefore conclude that the organisation of the mobility awards and the R&I Prize has been an interesting exercise exposing points of attention for further administrative simplification within the ENLIGHT consortium, but that in terms of bridging the gap between the different research communities and incentivizing joint research collaboration, efforts like focus groups (Task 2.3.1), Matchmaking events (Task 1.8) and the creation of research network through seed funding (see Deliverable D16) result more interesting for the researchers and more effective in outcome.

Annexes

Annex 1 – ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Award

⇒ As published December 22nd, 2022

ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Award

Call for mobility awards for R&I projects around ENLIGHT flagship areas between early career researchers¹ from different ENLIGHT consortium partners.

The [ENLIGHT consortium](#) intends to support new and ongoing joint R&I projects (proposals) jointly conducted by early career researchers from different (minimum two) ENLIGHT consortium partners. Thereto it will finance 20 mobility/travel awards – of up to maximum € 1,000.- each – to help deepen the envisioned plans for these joint collaborations.

The aim of this seed money is to stimulate and support (new) ENLIGHT RISE R&I collaborations and projects on [ENLIGHT flagship challenges](#) between early career researchers from various/different consortium partners.

Awarded projects making promising progress towards a consolidated joint R&I collaboration or project proposal after having received the mobility award will automatically be selected as candidates for the [ENLIGHT R&I Prize](#).

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The ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Award

The ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Award facilitates mobility/travel for promising joint collaborations – in research fields linked to the [5 ENLIGHT flagship domains](#) – between early career researchers from different ENLIGHT consortium partners. The aim is not only to enhance overall R&I collaborations between ENLIGHT consortium partners, moreover, to support early career researchers in expanding their network.

This seed money is intended to support the development stage or further elaboration of joint research activities conducted by early career researchers of different (minimum 2) ENLIGHT consortium partners, e.g. the initiation, design and/or development of one (or more) joint research proposals to be submitted to regional, national or international funding agencies including the Horizon Europe framework programme, etc.

This call therefore aims to facilitate in-person meetings and mobility between these early career researchers to concretize their collaboration, and/or to help them acquire necessary skills required to further elaborate their idea/project.

Applying researchers must contribute to the research mission of ENLIGHT, and hence focus on the development of (new) joint research initiatives amongst ENLIGHT partners. These research initiatives must focus on one of the [5 ENLIGHT flagship domains](#) and correspond to major societal challenges and priorities (health and well-being, climate action, energy transition and circular economy, digital innovation (AI / Open Science), and equity).

Applying proposals may apply for maximum three individual mobility awards (of max. € 1.000,- each) per project in case the application entails a joint participation to a conference, training or workshop.

Awardees of the ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Award will automatically be pre-selected for the [ENLIGHT R&I Prize](#) once their (progress) report (cf. below) has been accepted by the ENLIGHT R&I Prize Secretariat.

Criteria

Who can apply?

Early career researchers (including predoctoral researchers, PhD students as well as postdoctoral researchers and fellows) registered or employed at ENLIGHT partners who have obtained the PhD title no longer than 10 years prior to the submission date of their ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Award application.

Disciplinary field:

The call is open to proposals focussing on major societal challenges and priorities fitting in at least one of the five (5) [ENLIGHT flagship domains](#) (Health and Well-being, Climate change, Energy and Circular economy, Digital innovation and Impact of digitization, and Equity).

Activities eligible for funding:

The present call is targeted at the organization, creation, and exploration of (new) joint R&I activities and opportunities between ENLIGHT partners.

Activities eligible for funding:

- mobility to another ENLIGHT partner for in-person meetings to prepare/elaborate a joint R&I project (proposal);

- mobility of early career researchers from different ENLIGHT consortium partners to (jointly) attend a specialized conference, workshop, or training programme to enhance capacity needed for the preparation/elaboration of a joint R&I project (proposal).
- the activity (mobility) must be **conducted no later April 1st 2024**.
- an eligible project (or the reimbursed activity) must include members of minimum two different ENLIGHT partners.

Deadline

The call is open on a permanent basis until **December 15th, 2023**, however, will be automatically closed early once the maximum of 20 Mobility Awards has been awarded.

Selection

Starting January 2023, the selection commission will monthly select awardees amongst the received applications since the previous selection meeting.

The selection commission will be composed of the ENLIGHT-RISE WP2 assembly and will base its selection result upon suggestion by the WP2 co-leads.

The selection of proposals will be based on following criteria:

- Accordance with the [overall ENLIGHT objective/mission](#)
- Role of the applicant in the proposal
- Feasibility
- Innovative character
- Sustainability
- Involvement of the [Regional Academies](#) (i.e. focus on quadruple helix)

Financing

For each individual ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Award a maximum funding of € 1,000.- can be applied for.

Early career researchers may apply for maximum 1 mobility award. A total of 3 individual early careers researchers may apply for the same joint research initiative envisaged. In case of a positive evaluation, it will be up to the selection committee to decide how many mobility awards it will allocate to the same joint research initiative.

Only the mobility costs (travel and subsistence) and/or the inscription fees for a workshop, conference or training of the applicant(s) are eligible for funding.

Awardee's travel tickets (except for local transportation) and accommodation costs will be booked and directly financed by the ENLIGHT Consortium via the Financial Department of the University of Bordeaux (UBx) in accordance with the UBx travel guidelines. Subsistence allowance and possible inscription fees will be reimbursed upon the proven expenditure in accordance with the before mentioned guidelines.

Upon the selection of an ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Award, awardees will receive the UBx guidelines and contact information. Awardees will need to present a Mission Order by their home institution and send in all requested information and details for the booking of the mobility and/or fees for attending a conference, training, workshop, etc. at least 4 weeks before the date of departure.

The mobility award must be spent no later than April 1st, 2024. Expenses on a later date will in no case be eligible/funded.

How to apply?

Applications are made through the [designated form](#) and sent as a PDF-document to rise@ugent.be. The document should be named as follows:

ENLIGHT_R-I_ECR_Mobility_Award_-_surname_MainApplicant_name_MainApplicant

Report

Within one month after the end of the funded activity (and/or **no later the May 1st, 2024**), a short report (max. 1 A4), signed by the main applicant, together with the proven expenditure, must be sent electronically to rise@ugent.be and ri.prizes@u-bordeaux.fr

The report should illustrate the progress of the idea/concept/project since the awarding of the ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Award and how the reimbursed activity has proven / will prove to be fruitful for the further elaboration of the joint research collaboration envisaged.

Upon acceptance of the report, the project will be notified of its pre-selection for the [ENLIGHT R&I Prize](#). Based on the received reports, one ENLIGHT R&I Prize will be selected in September 2023 and another one in May 2024.

Annex 2 – The ENLIGHT R&I Prize

The ENLIGHT R&I PRIZE

The ENLIGHT R&I Prize is an annual award intended to provide additional support to a promising project or project proposal jointly conducted by early career researchers from different (minimum 2) ENLIGHT consortium partners and focusing on one of the five ENLIGHT flagship domains.

The prize consists of a mobility award of up to € 5,000.- for participation in conferences, workshops or training programs that can strengthen the required capacity within the project team.

The aim of the prize is not only to further stimulate or support the development stage or further elaboration of joint research collaborations between ENLIGHT partners, but to also support ENLIGHT early career researchers in expanding their network.

Therefore, not only running research collaborations are eligible though even so are newly created joint research teams preparing e.g. the initiation, design and/or development of one (or more) joint research proposals to be submitted to regional, national or international funding agencies including the Horizon Europe framework programme, etc.

The ENLIGHT R&I Prize is strongly linked to the [ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Award](#). Moreover, the prize winner will be selected amongst the ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Awardees. Project teams can thus not directly apply for the ENLIGHT R&I Prize but will be considered for this seed funding initiative through their selection for the [ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Award](#) **and** the acceptance of their report (illustrating the progress of the idea/concept/project since the awarding of the [ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Award](#)).

A selection commission composed of experts on the [ENLIGHT flagship domains](#) (nominated by the ENLIGHT-RISE pilot focus groups) and one (1) task member per ENLIGHT-RISE WP2 co-lead partner university will pre-select the winner amongst the eligible ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Awardees, to be confirmed by the ENLIGHT-RISE WP2 assembly.

In line with the funding scheme of the Horizon H2020 SwafS ENLIGHT-RISE programme, one ENLIGHT R&I Prize winner will be selected in September 2023, and another one in May 2024. The selection will be based on the received (progress) reports of the ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility awardees by the date of selection.

The prize winners will need to use the € 5,000.- mobility award prior to 31/8/2024. Only the mobility costs (travel and subsistence) and/or the inscription fees for a workshop, conference or training of the winning project's team members fitting the ECR description as stated in the [ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Award call](#) are eligible for funding. Alike the ENLIGHT R&I ECR Mobility Award, prize winners' travel bookings, subsistence costs, and reimbursement of proven expenditures will need to be in accordance with the University of Bordeaux's administration regulations, requirements, and travel guidelines.

Annex 3 – ENLIGHT R&I Mobility Grant Awardees - Year 2

ENLIGHT R&I Mobility Grant Awardees - Year 2

	Name	Gender	Title	Home	Receiving	#partner universities	flagship	type activity	period	Title application	Extra information
	↓	↓	↓	Univers	Universit	involve	domain		mobility		↓
1	XX XX	M	Prof.	RUG	UGent	3	Digital	preparatory meeting	3 days	Humour and Conflict in the Digital Age (HACIDA)	writing on a HE proposal
2	XX XX	M	postdoc	UGent	UPV-EHS	3	Digital	preparatory meeting	3 days	Humour and Conflict in the Digital Age (HACIDA)	writing on a HE proposal
3	XX XX	F	postdoc	UGent	UU	2	Heath + Equity	exploratory	4 days	CONTRAPTION: CONTRibution of TRANsport to Processes of gentrificaTION	
4	XX XX	F	postdoc	UT	UGent	2	Heath	exploratory	3 days	TRANSFORM: Transportation Research Advancing New Strategies for Equity and Mobility	
5	XX XX	F	Prof.	UGent	RUG	2	Heath	exploratory	2 days	Neighbouring the initiatives for the early detection of Neurodevelopmental Disabilities - NND	
6	XX XX	F	postdoc	UGent	GAL	2	Heath	workshop + propsal writing	3 days	NEURO-BALANCE: Neurodevelopmental Disorder- Family Occupational Balance.	writing a MSCA DN
7	XX XX	F	prof.	UBx	UPV/EHS	2	Equity	workshop + propsal writing	2 days	Migrants, their languages and self-development within communities through education policies in Euskadi and Nouvelle Aquitaine.	group application 2
8	XX XX	F	Prof.	UPV/EHS	UBx	2	Equity	workshop + propsal writing	2 days	Migrants, their languages and self-development within communities through education policies in Euskadi and Nouvelle Aquitaine.	group application 1
9	XX XX	F	PhD-student	UGent	UT	2	Equity	Exploratory	3 days	ACCESS: Activity Patterns Contributing Individuals' Experienced Social Segregation	
10	XX XX	M	postdoc	GAL	UPV/EHS	3	Digital	preparatory meeting	5 days	Researching Journalism Innovation (RJI)	
11	XX XX	F	Prof.	UPV/EHS	UBx	2	Equity	workshop + propsal writing	2 days	Migrants, their languages and self-development within communities through education policies in Euskadi and Nouvelle Aquitaine.	group application 1
12	XX XX	F	PhD-student	UPV/EHS	UBx	2	Equity	workshop + propsal writing	2 days	Migrants, their languages and self-development within communities through education policies in Euskadi and Nouvelle Aquitaine.	group application 1
13	XX XX	f	postdoc	UBx	UPV/EHS	2	Equity	workshop + propsal writing	2 days	Migrants, their languages and self-development within communities through education policies in Euskadi and Nouvelle Aquitaine.	group application 2
14	XX XX	f	PhD-student	UBx	UPV/EHS	2	Equity	workshop + propsal writing	2 days	Migrants, their languages and self-development within communities through education policies in Euskadi and Nouvelle Aquitaine.	group application 2

Annex 4 – ENIGHT RISE R&I Mobility Awardees – total

	Name	Gender	Title	ECR / non-ECR	Home University	Receiving University	#partner universities involved	flagship domain	type activity	period mobility	Title application	extra information
1	xxx	F	PhD-student	ECR	UPV/EHU	UU	2	Climate change	participation in a course		Green Campus Enlight Network + GREENlight	single application
2	xxx	F	Lecturer	ECR	UU	GAL	2	Climate change	workshop + proposal writing	5 days	You Are Not Alone: Mapping Climate Anxiety in Higher Education	single application
3	xxx	m	prof.	ECR	UG	UGent	2	Digital	workshop + proposal writing	2 days	<i>Narrative Theory and the Play of Complexity</i> NARPLAYCOM	group application 4 > cancelled > joined group application 5
4	xxx	m	prof.	ECR	UG	UGent	2	Digital	workshop + proposal writing	2 days	<i>Narrative Theory and the Play of Complexity</i> NARPLAYCOM	group application 5
5	xxx	m	prof.	ECR	UG	UGent	2	Digital	workshop + proposal writing	2 days	<i>Narrative Theory and the Play of Complexity</i> NARPLAYCOM	group application 4, cancelled due to health reasons
6	xxx	m	prof.	non-ECR	UG	UGent	2	Digital	workshop + proposal writing	2 days	Narrative Theory and the Play of Complexity NARPLAYCOM	group application 5
7	xxx	f	postdoc	ECR	UBx	UPV/EHU	2	Equity	workshop + proposal writing	2 days	Migrants, their languages and self-development within communities through education policies in Euskadi and Nouvelle Aquitaine.	group application 1
8	xxx	f	PhD-student	ECR	UBx	UPV/EHU	2	Equity	workshop + proposal writing	2 days	Migrants, their languages and self-development within communities through education policies in Euskadi and Nouvelle Aquitaine.	group application 1
9	xxx	F	prof.	non-ECR	UBx	UPV/EHU	2	Equity	workshop + proposal writing	2 days	Migrants, their languages and self-development within communities through education policies in Euskadi and Nouvelle Aquitaine.	group application 1
10	xxx	F	PhD-student	ECR	UGent	UT	2	Equity	Exploratory	3 days	ACCESS: Activity Patterns Contributing Individuals' Experienced Social Segregation	cancelled due to moving to another university
11	xxx	F	Prof.	ECR	UPV/EHU	UBx	2	Equity	workshop + proposal writing	2 days	Migrants, their languages and self-development within communities through education policies in Euskadi and Nouvelle Aquitaine.	group application 2
12	xxx	F	Prof.	ECR	UPV/EHU	UBx	2	Equity	workshop + proposal writing	2 days	Migrants, their languages and self-development within communities through education policies in Euskadi and Nouvelle Aquitaine.	group application 2

13	xxx	F	PhD-student	ECR	UPV/EHU	UBx	2	Equity	workshop + proposal writing	2 days	Migrants, their languages and self-development within communities through education policies in Euskadi and Nouvelle Aquitaine.	group application 2
14	xxx	F	Ass prof	non-ECR	GAL	UPV/EHU	2	Health	knowledge exchange	2 days	Evaluating VERA framework for students communicating with people living with dementia in the Basque country.	Group application 7
15	xxx	F	Ass prof	ECR	GAL	UPV/EHU	2	Health	knowledge exchange	2 days	Evaluating VERA framework for students communicating with people living with dementia in the Basque country.	Group application 7
16	xxx	m	Msc.	ECR	GAL	UPV/EHU	2	Health	exploratory	3 days	Minimally invasive digital fluid pressure measurement technology	group application 3
17	xxx	F	postdoc	ECR	UGent	GAL	2	Health	workshop + proposal writing	3 days	NEURO-BALANCE: Neurodevelopmental Disorder- Family Occupational Balance.	group application
18	xxx	F	Prof.	ECR	UGent	RUG	2	Health	exploratory	2 days	Neighbouring the initiatives for the early detection of Neurodevelopmental Disabilities - NND	Single application
19	xxx	F	postdoc	ECR	UT	UGent	2	Health	exploratory	3 days	TRANSFORM: Transportation Research Advancing New Strategies for Equity and Mobility	Single application
20	xxx	F	postdoc	ECR	UGent	UU	2	Health + Equity	exploratory	4 days	CONTRAPTION: CONTRibution of TRANsport to Processes of gentrificaTION	Single application
21	xxx	M	Ass Prof	non-ECR	UBX	RUG	3	Climate change	proposal writing (ETN) + Workshop	2 days	Global production chains and sustainability	single application
22	xxx	M	postdoc	ECR	GAL	UPV/EHU	3	Digital	preparatory meeting	5 days	Researching Journalism Innovation (RJI)	single application
23	xxx	M	Prof.	ECR	UG	UGent	3	Digital	preparatory meeting	3 days	Humour and Conflict in the Digital Age (HACIDA)	Single application
24	xxx	M	postdoc	ECR	UGent	UPV/EHU	3	Digital	preparatory meeting	3 days	Humour and Conflict in the Digital Age (HACIDA)	Single application
25	xxx	f	Prof.	non-ECR	GAL	UPV/EHU	3	Health	exploratory	3 days	Minimally invasive digital fluid pressure measurement technology	group application 3
26	xxx	m	Dr.	ECR	GAL	UPV/EHU	4	Health	exploratory	3 days	Minimally invasive digital fluid pressure measurement technology	group application 3

27	xxx	F	Lecturer	non-ECR	RUG	GAL	4	Equity + Digital + Health	proposal writing (ETN)	2 days	3G4P + Accessible & Interdisciplinary AI Literacy Education Network: 3G4P + (AI)2 LEN	Group application 6
28	xxx	M	Prof.	ECR	UGOE	GAL	4	Equity + Digital + Health	proposal writing (ETN)	2 days	3G4P + Accessible & Interdisciplinary AI Literacy Education Network: 3G4P + (AI)2 LEN	Group application 6
29	xxx	F	Ass Prof	ECR	UPV/EHU	GAL	4	Equity + Digital + Health	proposal writing (ETN)	2 days	3G4P + Accessible & Interdisciplinary AI Literacy Education Network: 3G4P + (AI)2 LEN	Group application 6